

Shared anchors for floating wind turbines

Test SW_02

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1 Introduction

This data report details the experimental results of the centrifuge test campaign SW_02, conducted on 18 June 2024. The test program consisted of one monotonic loading test and two cyclic loading tests applied to suction anchors installed in normally consolidated clay. The objective was to investigate the anchor behaviour under different loading conditions.

2 General Information

The centrifuge testing involved three suction anchors embedded in a normally consolidated clay specimen. The test sequence included a monotonic load test to establish baseline capacity, followed by two cyclic loading tests. The cyclic tests aimed to observe the anchor response, specifically focusing on the accumulation of displacements and the post-cyclic load capacity. Speswhite kaolin was used to simulate the normally consolidated ground profile. The clay sample was prepared using a reconstitution method that involves the application of specific consolidation pressures, as described in the following sections.

This experiment was conducted within the framework of the ShareWind project: Shared Anchors for Floating Wind Turbines (Grant agreement 101106921, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3030/101106921>).

3 Model preparation

A circular container, with an internal diameter of 895 mm and a height of 700 mm, was used for the centrifuge experiment. The clay sample was prepared by consolidating Speswhite kaolin slurry in four distinct layers. Each layer was subjected to a different pre-consolidation pressure to achieve a profile representative of normally consolidated clay (details provided in Table 1). Kaolin was initially mixed with water to achieve a target initial water content of approximately 80% for all layers. To calculate the in situ stress profile, a total unit weight of the clay $\gamma = 16.6 \text{ kN/m}^3$ and an effective unit weight $\gamma' = 6.5 \text{ kN/m}^3$ were assumed. The effective vertical target stresses were determined at different depths assuming a model-prototype scale factor of $N = 75$.

Table 1: Consolidation pressures and clay layers thickness - Model SW02

	Model			Prototype				Model - Prototype
	From (mm)	To (mm)	Thickness (mm)	From (m)	To (m)	Thickness (m)	Average Depth (m)	Average vertical stress (kPa)
Layer 4	0.0	99.0	99.0	0.0	7.4	7.4	3.7	24.5
Layer 3	99.0	185.0	86.0	7.4	13.9	6.5	10.7	70.3
Layer 2	185.0	266.0	81.0	13.9	20.0	6.1	16.9	111.6
Layer 1	266.0	340.0	74.0	20.0	25.5	5.6	22.7	150.0
	Total		340 mm	Total		25.5 m		

Figure 1: Target vertical effective stress profile for the clay and pre-consolidation pressures

Before placing the first clay layer, a 100 mm thick layer of sand was installed at the base of the model container. This sand layer facilitated the drainage of the overlying clay during consolidation. Consolidation pressures were applied using a hydraulic piston equipped with a digital control system for pressure regulation. The minimum applied pressure, corresponding to the piston's self-weight, was 6.9 kPa; this constituted the initial pressure on each newly placed layer before further consolidation increments were applied. Figure 2 illustrates the loading system and the placement of a clay layer within the container.

Table 2 summarizes the initial and final thicknesses of the reconstituted clay layers after consolidation to the target pressures specified previously (in Table 1).

Figure 2: Setup for the consolidation of the clay

Table 2: Consolidation of clay layers and loading sequence

	H0 - Initial height(mm)	Hf - Final height (mm)	Hf/Ho	Load Sequence (kPa)
Clay 4 (Top)	120.0	99.0	0.83	6.9 - 24.0
Clay 3	120.0	86.0	0.72	6.9 - 15.0 - 28.0 -70.0
Clay 2	120.0	81.0	0.68	6.9 - 15.0 - 28.0 - 60.0 - 112.0
Clay 1 (bottom)	110.0	74.0	0.67	6.9 - 14.0 -28.0-60.0 -150.0
Total	470.0	340.0		

4 Experimental setup

Three suction anchors were installed in the prepared clay specimen for subsequent monotonic and cyclic load testing. A model-prototype scale factor of $N=75$ was adopted, consistent with previous centrifuge testing at the Gustave Eiffel University laboratory (Cathie et al., 2020). Table 3 lists the key model dimensions and their equivalent prototype values. The initial height of the prepared clay specimen before the centrifuge test commenced was 340 mm. Following re-consolidation under increased self-weight in flight (at 75g acceleration), the final height of the clay bed reduced to 330 mm. This reduction corresponds to an additional settlement of approximately 10 mm induced by the increased gravitational field.

The centrifuge model was instrumented with pore pressure transducers (PPTs) embedded within the clay at four primary locations, defined relative to the anchor geometry (where D is the anchor diameter, specified in Table 3):

- At a depth equivalent to one diameter ($1D$) below the anchor base.
- At a depth corresponding to the anchor base level.
- At a depth corresponding to the anchor top (inside the anchor).

These PPTs were installed progressively during the preparation and consolidation of the different clay layers.

An LVDT was positioned on the clay surface to monitor settlements during re-consolidation in flight of the model; Additionally, potentiometers and laser transducers were installed to monitor anchor displacements during testing as described in the following sections. The actuator used to apply loads was instrumented with a load cell (for force measurement) and a laser displacement sensor (for monitoring actuator position). Characterization of the undrained shear strength (s_u) profile of the consolidated clay specimen was performed in flight using a T-bar penetrometer. The T-bar had a diameter of 5 mm and a shaft length of 20 mm, resulting in a projected area of 100 mm².

Table 3: Prototype and model dimensions

Dimension	Model (1/75)	Prototype
Suction anchor		
Material	Stainless steel	–
D (diameter)	60 mm	4.5 m
L (length)	200 mm	15.0 m
L/D	3.3	3.3
t (wall thickness)	0.41 mm	3.0 cm
D/t	150	150
W (weight)	256.3 g	1.08 MN
W' (buoyant weight)	218.5 g	0.903 MN
Model Container		
Height	700 mm	52.5 m
Height extension	160 mm	12.0 m
Diameter	895 mm	67.1 m
Water table	50 mm	3.75 m
Soil layers		
Clay 4 (Top)	99 mm	7.4 m
Clay 3	86 mm	6.5 m
Clay 2	81 mm	6.1 m
Clay 1 (bottom)	74 mm	5.6 m

The anchors were installed at 1g by manually pushing them into the clay. The installation depth corresponded to the full length of the anchors (200 mm). This process was carried out by opening the top valves of the anchors to let the air inside the caisson flow out (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Suction anchors installation

In the sequence, a pore pressure transducer (PPT) was pushed throughout a 5 mm diameter opening of the valve. The valve is equipped with internal O-rings that seal the space between the PPT cable and the valve opening. Figure 4 illustrates the installation procedure of a PPT at the top of an anchor.

Figure 4: Installation of a PPT on top of an anchor

During the installation of the anchors, some remoulding around the anchor-clay interface may occur. To account for this, the model with the anchors installed was kept in-flight during the centrifuge test for approximately 5 hours (model scale) before the loading tests. This ensured a setup time for the anchors equivalent to 38 months at the prototype scale, thereby guaranteeing a uniform stress field for the loading tests.

Following anchor installation, a loading frame comprising gantries and supports was assembled above the model container. This frame supported the unidirectional electric actuator used to apply controlled loads to the anchors. The configuration of the loading system relative to the anchors is depicted in Figure 5 and Figure 6. Figure 7 shows additional details of the experimental setup including a view of the model anchors, the installation process and the setup to monitor the anchor displacements.

Anchor rotation during testing was derived from displacement measurements. Two laser transducers (identified as sensors D161 and D159), mounted on an extension piece above the anchor's load attachment point, and two potentiometers (identified as sensors D151 and D37), positioned to measure lateral displacements, were employed for this calculation. The horizontal separation distance between the pair of laser transducers (D161, D159) was 80 mm, while the separation between the pair of potentiometers (D151, D37) was 47 mm (see Figure 14 for further details). These known geometric separations allowed the differential displacements recorded by each pair of sensors to be converted into angles of rotation.

Figure 5: Test SW02 setup and instrumentation -side view

Figure 6: Test SW02 setup and instrumentation -plan view

Figure 7: Test SW02 - Details of the centrifuge setup

5 Test chronology

The centrifuge test was carried out in three stages that took place in three consecutive days as follows:

- Day 1 (18-June-2024): lateral monotonic load test on anchor 2.
- Day 2 (19-June-2024): lateral cyclic load on anchor 1
- Day 3 (20-June-2024): lateral cyclic load on anchor 3.

5.1 Anchor 1 - Lateral load test

This test consisted of applying a monotonic load on top of the suction anchor at a loading rate of 23 mm/min:

- 11h00: Start of the data acquisition at a frequency of 1 Hz.
- 11h00: Start of the centrifuge test.
- 11h30: Arrival at the testing level of 75g.
- 11h30 to 15h00: re-consolidation of the clay.
- 15h30: T-bar test #1 at a load rate of 3 mm/s and sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- 16h00: lateral load test at a load rate of 23 mm/min and sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- 16h00: video recording of the lateral test.
- 16h30: T-bar test #2 at a load rate of 3 mm/s and sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- 17h:00 stop the data acquisition at a frequency of 1 Hz.
- 17h:00 end of the centrifuge test.

5.2 Anchor 2 - Lateral cyclic load test

This test consisted of a pull-out test at a loading rate of 0.2 Hz (0.0027 Hz or a period of 375 s/cycle at prototype scale):

- 09h30: Start of the data acquisition at a frequency of 1 Hz.
- 09h30: Start of the centrifuge test.
- 09h55: Arrival at the testing level of 75g.
- 09h55 to 14h00: re-consolidation of the clay.
- 14h00: T-bar test #3 at a load rate of 3 mm/s and sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- 14h00: video recording of the lateral test.
- 14h00: cyclic load test distributed in 4 load packages of increasing amplitude sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- 17h00: stop the data acquisition at a frequency of 1 Hz.
- 17h00: end of the centrifuge test.

5.3 Anchor 3 - Lateral cyclic load test

This test consisted on applying monotonic load on top of the suction anchor at a loading rate of 0.2 Hz at model scale (0.0027 Hz or a period of 375 s/cycle at prototype scale):

- 09h19: Start of the data acquisition at a frequency of 1 Hz.
- 09h19: Start of the centrifuge test.
- 09h45: Arrival at the testing level of 75g.
- 09h45 to 14h00: re-consolidation of the clay.
- 14h02: T-bar test #4 at a load rate of 3 mm/s and sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- 14h30: video recording of the lateral test.
- 14h30: cyclic load test distributed in 3 load packages of increasing amplitude sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- 17h15: stop the data acquisition at a frequency of 1 Hz.
- 17h15: end of the centrifuge test.

6 Test Results

The results presented in this section are given at **model scale**. To obtain the equivalent **prototype scale** values, the appropriate scaling laws must be applied using a model-prototype scale factor of $N=75$. The inclination angle of the loads applied to the anchors was 45° ($\alpha = 45$ in Figure 5 and Figure 8)

6.1 Pullout test - Anchor 1

Figure 8 presents the raw data obtained from the inclined pullout test performed on Anchor 1. During this test, the load was applied via a padeye located at a depth corresponding to two-thirds of the anchor's embedded length. The raw data represent model-scale results, calculated using instrument calibration factors stored in the laboratory's database. Data acquisition was performed using an HBK QuantumX system (HBK QuantumX details). The presented data (Figure ??) include the force measured by the actuator's load cell plotted against the corresponding displacement applied by the actuator.

Pore pressure measurements included in this dataset were recorded at three locations within the soil specimen, identified by their sensor IDs:

- Below the anchor base at a depth of 1D (Sensor P175).
- At the anchor base (Sensor P180).
- At the anchor top (Sensor P177).

Note that all pore pressure measurements shown in the figures within this report were set to zero at the beginning of each load test (both monotonic and cyclic). Consequently, the presented pore pressure transducer (PPT) data represent the change in pore pressure relative to the initial state before loading (Δu or Delta Pore Pressure).

Figure 8: Anchor 1: anchor response under monotonic load applied at the anchor padeye inclined 45 degrees.

6.2 Cyclic load tests - Anchor 2 and Anchor 3

Figure 9 presents the results from the cyclic lateral load tests performed on suction anchor 2. The presented data display the lateral force, measured by the actuator's load cell, plotted against the corresponding horizontal displacement imposed by the actuator during the cyclic loading sequence.

Pore pressure measurements are presented from the following operational transducers, with locations defined relative to the tested anchor:

- At an elevation corresponding to the anchor base (Sensor P174).
- At an elevation corresponding to the anchor top (Sensor P177).

It should be noted that the pore pressure transducer (PPT) positioned 1D (one diameter) below the anchor base malfunctioned during this test and consequently did not yield reliable data.

Figure 9: Anchor 2: anchor response under cyclic load applied at the anchor padeye inclined 45 degrees.

Figure 10 presents time histories recorded during the cyclic loading test, plotting the applied load, measured excess pore pressures, and calculated anchor rotations against time, all at model scale. The anchor rotations shown were calculated using displacement data from potentiometers D151 and D37 (as described previously).

The test sequence involved four load packages with varying numbers of cycles: 500 cycles were applied for each of packages P1, P2, and P3, followed by 240 cycles for package P4.

During the application of load package P4, a structural failure of the loading padeye occurred. Consequently, a planned post-cyclic monotonic load test, intended to follow the cyclic loading phase, could not be conducted.

Figure 10: Anchor 2: anchor response under cyclic load - time histories of load, excess pore pressures and calculated rotations.

6.3 Cyclic load tests -Anchor 3

Figure 11 shows the load-displacement response recorded during the testing of Anchor 3, along with the evolution of excess pore pressure measured at the anchor top (Sensor P177). The results cover both the cyclic loading phase and the subsequent post-cyclic monotonic pullout.

During this test, the pore pressure transducers (PPTs) positioned level with the anchor base and at a depth of one diameter (1D) below the anchor base malfunctioned. Consequently, unreliable data were obtained from these two sensors, and only the top PPT (P177) data is presented.

The cyclic loading phase applied to Anchor 3 consisted of three load packages (P1, P2, and P3), each comprising 500 cycles. This cyclic phase was followed by a monotonic load application. The monotonic pullout was continued until a plateau, indicating that peak resistance had been reached, was observed in the load-displacement curve.

The control strategy for the monotonic loading involved two stages. Initially, the load application was conducted under displacement control, primarily to ensure the loading line

became taut. Subsequently, the actuator's control mode was switched to load control for the remainder of the monotonic test until completion.

Figure 11: Anchor 3: anchor response under cyclic load applied at the anchor padeye inclined 45 degrees.

Figure 12 presents time histories recorded during the load test of anchor 3. It illustrates the sequence of applied load packages, the evolution of excess pore pressures (from the operational sensors P177), and the calculated anchor rotations, all plotted against time at model scale.

The anchor rotations depicted in this figure were calculated based on displacement measurements obtained from the laser transducers identified as D161 and D159.

Figure 12: Anchor 3: anchor response under cyclic load - time histories of load, excess pore pressures and calculated rotations.

6.4 Strength characterization tests

Figure 13 displays the results obtained from the T-bar penetrometer characterization tests, presenting the derived undrained shear strength (s_u) profile of the clay specimen after consolidation in flight.

As detailed previously (e.g., in Section 4), the T-bar penetrometer utilized for these tests had a diameter of 5 mm and a length of 20 mm, corresponding to a projected bearing area of $A = 100 \text{ mm}^2$.

The s_u profile shown in Figure 13 was calculated from the continuous measurements recorded during penetration. Specifically, the penetration force (F) measured by a load cell integrated with the T-bar actuator, and the corresponding penetration depth, determined from the T-bar actuator potentiometer readings, were used.

Notably, in this figure, the undrained shear strength is plotted against depth, with the depth axis presented at prototype scale (applying the scale factor $N=75$). This presentation facilitates the direct comparison of the strength profile with relevant full-scale depths for foundation or anchor embedment analysis.

Figure 13: Undrained shear strength profiles: T-bar test and hand vane data

For the calculations of the undrained shear strength profiles, it was employed the following relationship:

$$s_u = \frac{q}{N_t} \quad (1)$$

Where (F = T-bar measured force, A =T-bar projected area),

$$q = F/A \quad (2)$$

and $N_t = 10.5$ corresponding to the T-bar factor (Stewart and Randolph, 1991).

7 Data sets

The datasets provided with this report are presented entirely at model scale. Users must apply the appropriate scaling laws to convert these model-scale results to equivalent prototype-scale values for the different physical quantities involved (e.g., force, displacement, time, pore

pressure). These scaling principles are well-established and detailed in standard literature concerning geotechnical centrifuge modelling (Madabhushi, 2014).

Consideration and correct application of these scaling relationships are essential when interpreting or utilizing the provided data for analyses relevant to the prototype scale. A summary of the scaling laws employed in centrifuge modelling is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Scaling laws employed in centrifuge modelling, Madabhushi, 2014

Parameter	Scaling law (model/prototype)	Units
<i>General scaling laws (slow events)</i>		
Length	$1/N$	m
Area	$1/N^2$	m ²
Volume	$1/N^3$	m ³
Mass	$1/N^3$	kg
Stress	1	N/m ²
Strain	1	–
Force	$1/N^2$	N
Bending moment	$1/N^3$	Nm
Work	$1/N^3$	Nm
Energy	$1/N^3$	J
Seepage velocity	N	m/s
Time (consolidation)	$1/N^2$	s
<i>Dynamic events</i>		
Time (dynamic)	$1/N$	s
Frequency	N	s ⁻¹
Displacement	$1/N$	m
Velocity	1	m/s
Acceleration (incl. gravity)	N	m/s ²

The provided datasets contain the raw data as recorded by the data logging system during the experiments. Users should note that these are unprocessed readings; appropriate offsets must be applied to instrument readings (e.g., load cells, pore pressure transducers) to establish a zero baseline relative to the start of each test phase before calculating net loads or excess pore pressures.

To ensure broad accessibility, the data files are provided in two formats:

- The proprietary MATLAB (.mat) file format, suitable for users with access to MATLAB software.
- The non-proprietary Comma Separated Values (.csv) file format, compatible with a wide range of spreadsheet programs, data analysis tools, and programming languages.

Additionally, a utility script (e.g., specify if MATLAB, Python, etc.) is included with the dataset. This script allows users to convert the .mat files into the .csv format if required.

7.1 Load tests

For the project, the data sets for the loading tests are identified following this structure:

SW_x_xx_xxx_xxxx

Where,

SW	Abbreviation of the project name ShareWind
x	Test number: 01, 02, 03 ...
xx	Anchor identifier: 1, 2, 3.
xxx	Load type: H(horizontal), V (vertical), I (inclined), M (multidirectional)
xxxx	MO (monotonic), CY (cyclic)

For example, data set SW_02_1_H_MO corresponds to test 02, on anchor 1, subjected to horizontal load (H), monotonic (MO).

7.2 T-bar tests

For the T-bar tests, the data sets are identified as follows:

SW_y-yy-yyy

Where,

SW	Abbreviation of the project name ShareWind
y	Test number: 01, 02, 03 ...
yy	T-bar consecutive identifier: TBAR1, TBAR2, TBAR3.
yyy	MO (monotonic), CY (cyclic)

For example, data set SW_02 TBAR1 _MO corresponds to centrifuge test 01, T-bar number 1 of type monotonic (MO).

7.3 Data files

The provided data files contain the time-series recordings from the various sensors employed during the experiments to monitor the response of the suction anchors under different loading conditions. This includes measurements from load cells, operational pore pressure transducers, and displacement sensors (LVDTs, potentiometers, laser transducers), among others.

For clarity, especially regarding the calculation of anchor kinematics, Figure 14 provides a schematic diagram identifying the specific labels of the displacement transducers used to determine anchor rotations (i.e., laser transducers D161 and D159, and potentiometers D151 and D37).

Figure 14: Raw data - Lateral load - Model scale

The loading tests, horizontal (H) and vertical (V) contain several columns organised as follows:

File **SW_02_1_I_MO**:

Column	Id	Description
1	time	Measurement time in seconds
2	F162	Force recorded by the actuator, applied to the anchor in N
3	D159	Displacement recorded by one laser on top of the extension piece attached to the anchor, in mm
4	D37_pot	Lateral displacement recorded by a potentiometer, in mm
5	D151_pot	Lateral displacement recorded by a potentiometer, in mm
6	P177_TOP_A1	Pore pressure transducer at the top of the anchor, in Kpa
7	P180_BASE_A1	Pore pressure transducer at the base of the anchor, in Kpa
8	P175_1D_A1	Pore pressure transducer at 1D below the base of the anchor, in kPa
9	D161	Displacement recorded by one laser on top of the extension piece attached to the anchor, in mm
10	Disp_SVH300_SSI	Displacement recorded by the actuator, the applied to the anchor, in mm

File **SW_02_2_I_CY**:

Column	Id	Description
1	time	Measurement time in seconds
2	F162	Force recorded by the actuator, applied to the anchor in N
3	D159	Displacement recorded by one laser on top of the extension piece attached to the anchor, in mm
4	D37_pot	Lateral displacement recorded by a potentiometer, in mm
5	D151_pot	Lateral displacement recorded by a potentiometer, in mm
6	P177_TOP_A2	Pore pressure transducer at the top of the anchor, in Kpa
7	D161	Displacement recorded by one laser on top of the extension piece attached to the anchor, in mm
8	P174_BASE_A2	Pore pressure transducer at the base of the anchor, in kPa
9	Disp_SVH300_SSI	Displacement recorded by the actuator, the applied to the anchor, in mm

File **SW_02_3_I_CY**:

Column	Id	Description
1	time	Measurement time in seconds
2	F162	Force recorded by the actuator, applied to the anchor in N
3	D159	Displacement recorded by one laser on top of the extension piece attached to the anchor, in mm
4	D37_pot	Lateral displacement recorded by a potentiometer, in mm
5	P177_TOP_A3	Pore pressure transducer at the top of the anchor, in Kpa
6	D161	Displacement recorded by one laser on top of the extension piece attached to the anchor, in mm
7	P170_BASE_A3	Pore pressure transducer at the base of the anchor, in kPa - MALFUNCTION
8	P129_1D_A3	Pore pressure transducer at 1D below the base of the anchor, in kPa - MALFUNCTION
9	Disp_SVH300_SSI	Displacement recorded by the actuator, the applied to the anchor, in mm

The T-bar tests contain three columns organised as follows:

Column	Id	Description
1	time	Measurement time in seconds
2	F_Tbar	Force recorded by the T-bar load cell in DaN
3	z_Tbar	Displacement recorded by the T-bar actuator in mm

7.4 Other files

Several water content samples were obtained from the clay specimen both before the start of centrifuge testing and after its completion to evaluate the changes resulting from consolidation and loading.

The data file `SW_02_water_content.csv` contains the water content values measured from the post-test samples. In addition, the average water content value measured from the clay slurry before the consolidation process began is also included in this file; this pre-consolidation value is labeled as 'initial' in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Raw data - Lateral load - Model scale

The geometry of the experimental setup of the loading tests is provided in .DXF files that can be opened in any Computed Asisted Design (CAD) application. The files are identified as follows:

SW_D_DD_SETUP.dxf

Where,

SW	Abbreviation of the project name ShareWind
D	Test number: 01, 02, 03 ...
DD	Anchor identifier: A01, A02,A03

8 Associated publications

Further analysis about the data presented in this data report can be found at:

Soriano, C., Thorel, L., & Blanc, M. (2025, June 9–13). Centrifuge modeling of cyclic loading on suction anchors in soft clay. In *Proceedings of the 5th International Symposium on Frontiers in Offshore Geotechnics (ISFOG 2025)*, Nantes, France.

9 References

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